

The Fast Food Image Classification using Deep Learning

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Abstract: Fast food refers to quick, convenient, and ready-to-eat meals that are usually sold at chain restaurants or take-out establishments. Fast food is often criticized for its unhealthy ingredients, such as high levels of salt, sugar, and unhealthy fats, and its contribution to the growing obesity epidemic. Despite this, fast food remains popular due to its affordability, convenience, and widespread availability. Many fast food chains have attempted to respond to these criticisms by offering healthier options, such as salads and grilled chicken sandwiches, and by using more natural and locally sourced ingredients. The aim in this paper to propose a deep learning model for the classification of fast food dishes. The proposed model, Xception, was trained on natural images and was fine-tuned to make up the fast food meals. The researchers collected the Fast Food V2 dataset from Kaggle depository, the dataset, contained 20,000 images. The dataset has ten labels of food images comprised of Baked Potato, Burger, Crispy Chicken, Donut, Fries, Hot Dog, Pizza, Sandwich, Taco, and Taquito. The dataset was split into three sets: training, validation and testing. The accuracy, F1-score, recall, precision on the separate test set showed that classification of fast food was accuracy (95.13%), Precision (95.34%), Recall (95.13%), and F1-Score (95.14%).

Keywords DCNN, Classification, Fast Food, Deep Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in food obesity has led to a higher risk of various obesity-related diseases such as type-2 diabetes, cancer, heart disease, and, due to excessive calorie intake [1]. To combat this, there is a need for an efficient dietary assessment system that can classify fast food images, in an effort to reduce the risk of food obesity [2]-[3].

Recent research has proposed using supervised machine-learning systems to address the limitations of traditional food recognition and classification methods [4]-[10]. Machine-learning techniques such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and Classification and Regression Trees (CART) have been employed in the classifications [11][20]. However, the performance of these conventional machine-learning techniques is not optimal due to the need for manual feature engineering to train the model and make accurate predictions from the datasets. The latest trend in this field is the use of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) techniques, which are based on deep learning, to handle the complex relationships between the image class and datasets [21]-[23]. This makes CNNs particularly suitable for food classification based on images.

CNN learning has significant advantages in terms of image classification and recognition, especially in food classification. The CNN model consists of multiple layers at different levels of abstraction to learn the features of datasets and has been successful in applications such as character recognition [24], face recognition [25], food identification [26], cooking method recognition [27], herbal medicine image recognition [28] food ingredient detection, and fake-food image recognition [29]. Thus, it is expected that CNN will be effective in food classification. However, this still requires investigation and validation, as CNN can be sensitive

to factors such as the number of datasets, filter size, regularization, number of feature maps, and activation function. Current food classification algorithms also have limitations, including low accuracy, high processing time, and large weight matrices of the neural network. The best model is one that balances accuracy with processing time and reduces the weight matrices of the neural network. Recent studies of CNN-based food image classification have employed various techniques and algorithms to improve accuracy during the learning and testing phases. The classification accuracy based on CNN was 3.40% higher than SVM-based classification [30].

However, the current classification accuracy results remain low, which may be attributed to factors such as the number of datasets, filter size, regularization, number of feature maps, and activation function. There is still much room for improvement in this field.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The objective of this section is to survey existing studies, identify gaps, and provide a comprehensive overview of different tools, methodologies and techniques used in the related field of study. It also offers a critical evaluation of prior research and perspectives on various studies. The literature review focusing on classification of fast food dishes.

In [31], they assessed the accuracy of the classification component in their dietary assessment algorithm using various visual descriptors and classifiers, including a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier, which achieved an accuracy of 78.90%. They compared the performance of the SVM to that of the K-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN) classifier and found that SVM was a better option. Image segmentation was taken into account during the implementation of this model. However, the classification accuracy was low and SVM and

K-NN are not deep learning techniques. Thus, the algorithm appears to not support the proposed system for food classification and calorie prediction using deep learning.

In [32], they studied the accuracy of food and drink image dataset classification and detection using the NutriNet Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCN) architecture system, resulting in 86.72% classification accuracy and 94.47% image detection accuracy. However, the DCN system was only designed for binary classification with two classes: food and drink, so it may not fully support the proposed food classification system.

In [33], they assessed the accuracy of Chinese character classification in a character recognition task using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCN) system with three convolutional layers, two max-pooling layers, and a fully-connected layer, resulting in a classification accuracy of 82%. Further improvement could be made by incorporating image segmentation. The use of convolutional layers, max-pooling layers, and a fully-connected layer in the DCN model supports the proposed system.

In [34], they evaluated the accuracy of image classification for various food image datasets using two pertained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithms, ResNet-152 and GoogleNet, along with Artificial Neural Network, Support Vector Machine with RBF kernel (SVM-RBF), and Random Forest classifiers. The results showed an accuracy of 98.8%, which was an improvement over existing solutions using a combination of these classifiers. Despite this high accuracy, the use of SVM-RBF and Random Forest classifiers, which are not deep learning techniques, suggests that there may be limited potential for further improvement in the proposed food classification.

In [35], they studied the accuracy of image classification by combining a mixed-scale dilated convolutions network with a dense network, resulting in a class accuracy of 63.9% and a global accuracy of 87.0% with 200 layers. Although the global accuracy was high, the class accuracy was not substantial enough to achieve accurate calorie prediction. Hence, this combination of dilated convolutions network and deep network algorithm does not support the proposed food classification system.

In [36], they evaluated the classification accuracy for an automated food recognition system using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCN). This resulted in a classification accuracy of 82.29% with precision of 66.37%, recall 65.84%, and an F1 score of 66.17%. Although this is an improvement over the existing food classification techniques

using DCN, the low precision, recall, and F1 score values could lead to misclassification of food images and failure in calorie prediction. Despite this, the use of DCN in the solution is valuable to the proposed food classification system.

In [37], they evaluated the accuracy of food image recognition algorithms using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with image segmentation and image cropping. The study resulted in a top-1 accuracy of 77% and top-5 accuracy of 94.0%. Additionally, they examined the energy consumption for image analysis and image transferring, with values of 0.51 joules and 0.5 J, respectively. This was an improvement over previous CNN solutions. Hence, this algorithm can provide support to the proposed food classification system.

In [38], they examined the accuracy of the algorithm for recognizing multi-item food images. They achieved this by utilizing Convolutional Neural Network feature extraction, region mining, and classifier training, resulting in a recognition accuracy of 94.11% and a recall rate of 90.98% and precision rate of 93.05%. Although this is an improvement from the previous Convolutional Neural Network solution with a classification accuracy of 94.11%, the use of region collection, region mining, and pre-training in this system suggests that it provides support to the proposed food classification and calorie prediction system.

From the previous studies, we can see that the employed datasets are somewhat different from the one we are using, the CNN and Machine learning models used are not the same as the one we are proposing Xception model; furthermore, the accuracy achieved in the previous studies in terms of deep learning models came between [78.90% - 94.11%]. Thus there is a room for improvement in terms of Accuracy.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Dataset

The fast food V2 dataset was collected from Kaggle website. The dataset consists of 20,000 images of 10 different fast food classes. The 10 classes are Baked Potato, Burger, Crispy Chicken, Donut, Fries, Hot Dog, Pizza, Sandwich, Taco, and Taquito.

The dataset was resized, cropped, and normalized. The fast food V2 already split into Train, Valid, and Test sets. The Train set has 15000 images where each class has 1500 images. The Valid set consists of 3500 images where each class has 350 images. The Test set has 1500 images where some classes has 100 images and the other classes has 200 images.

Figure 1 presents some samples of the fast food V2 dataset.

Fig. 1. Samples from the fast food V2 dataset

3.2 Proposed model

The proposed model Xception was fine-tuning for the classification of the fast food dataset (Figure 2). Xception is a deep convolutional neural network architecture for image classification tasks. It was introduced in 2016 by François Chollet and is built on top of the concept of "depthwise separable convolutions". Unlike traditional convolutional layers, depthwise separable convolutions split the convolution operation into two separate steps: a depthwise convolution that operates on each channel of the input, and a pointwise convolution that combines the results. This design allows for a more efficient use of computational resources and reduces the number of parameters in the model, making it faster to train and less prone to overfitting.

Xception also utilizes "residual connections" which bypasses some of the intermediate layers and adds their inputs directly to the outputs, allowing the network to learn residual representations. Xception has been applied to a variety of computer vision tasks and has achieved state-of-the-art

performance on several benchmark datasets for image classification, such as ImageNet.

The architecture of Xception can be summarized as follows (Figure 2):

- Initial Convolution layer: This layer applies a traditional convolution operation to the input image to produce a feature map.
- Depthwise Separable Convolutions: A series of depthwise separable convolution blocks are applied to the feature map, with each block consisting of a depthwise convolution layer followed by a pointwise convolution layer. The depthwise convolution layer operates on each channel of the input, while the pointwise convolution layer combines the results.
- Residual Connections: Some of the intermediate layers are bypassed, and their inputs are added directly to the outputs, allowing the network to learn residual representations.
- Max Pooling: The feature maps are down-sampled by applying max pooling layers.

- Fully Connected Layers: A series of fully connected layers are used for classification, mapping the feature maps to the output class scores.

Fig. 2. Fine-tuned Xception Architecture

3.3 Training and validating the proposed model

After we have finished pre-processing of the images we kept training and validating the proposed model once using augmentation for 20 epochs and another 20 epochs without

augmentation until we reached the highest accuracy possible. Figure 3 show the history of training and validation for a 20 epochs while Figure 4 shows the history of the training and validation Loss for a 20 epochs.

Figure 3. History of training and validation accuracy for a 20 epochs

Figure 4. History of training and validation Loss for a 20 epochs

3.4 Evaluating the proposed model

There are several evaluation metrics commonly used to assess the performance of the Xception model for fast food V2 dataset. We have used the following metrics:

- Accuracy: Proportion of correct predictions among all instances as in equation 1.
- Precision: Proportion of correct positive predictions among all positive predictions made as in equation 2.
- Recall: Proportion of positive instances that were correctly classified among all positive instances as in equation 3.
- F1-Score: Harmonic mean of precision and recall as in equation 4.
- Confusion Matrix: A matrix that summarizes the performance of a classifier by counting the number of true positive, false positive, false negative, and true negative predictions.
- ROC Curve: A plot of the true positive rate against the false positive rate. It is used to visualize the

performance of a classifier and choose a threshold for class predictions.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \tag{2}$$

$$F1 - \text{score} = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \tag{3}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TN + TP}{TN + FP + TP + FN} \tag{4}$$

Where: FP = False Positive; FN = False Negative; TP = True Positive; TN = True Negative

Figure 5 outline the classification report of the Xception model which include the Precision, Recall, F1-Score, supporting number of images for each class in the fast food V2 dataset. Furthermore, it include the overall accuracy, Macro Average, and weighted Average.

From Figure 5, the proposed model achieved accuracy (95.13%), Precision (95.34%), Recall (95.13%), and F1-Score (95.14%).

ROC Curve for the proposed Xception model is greater than 0.99 for each class in the fast food V2 dataset as can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 7 show the confusion matrix that summarizes the performance of the Xception model by counting the number of true positive, false positive, false negative, and true negative predictions.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Baked Potato	0.9406	0.9500	0.9453	100
Burger	0.9894	0.9350	0.9614	200
Crispy Chicken	0.9074	0.9800	0.9423	100
Donut	0.9848	0.9700	0.9773	200
Fries	0.9510	0.9700	0.9604	100
Hot Dog	0.9637	0.9300	0.9466	200
Pizza	0.9652	0.9700	0.9676	200
Sandwich	0.9561	0.9800	0.9679	200
Taco	0.8291	0.9700	0.8940	100
Taquito	0.9540	0.8300	0.8877	100
accuracy			0.9513	1500
macro avg	0.9441	0.9485	0.9451	1500
weighted avg	0.9534	0.9513	0.9514	1500

Fig. 5. Classification report of the Xception proposed model

Fig. 6. The ROC Curve of each class in Fast Food V2 Dataset

[95	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	1]
[0	187	0	1	0	3	0	7	2	0]
[0	0	98	0	2	0	0	0	0	0]
[1	0	1	194	0	2	2	0	0	0]
[1	0	1	0	97	0	0	0	0	1]
[0	1	1	2	0	186	3	1	4	2]
[1	1	1	0	1	0	194	1	1	0]
[1	0	0	0	0	0	1	196	2	0]
[1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	97	0]
[1	0	2	0	2	1	0	0	11	83]

Fig. 7. Confusion Matrix

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To compare the performance of the previous studies with the current study, the dataset should be the same in both previous studies and current study; furthermore, the CNN model should be the same. Even though the previous studies used somewhat different datasets and different CNN models and Machine learning, the current study achieved much better accuracies than the previous studies. The proposed model in current study achieved accuracy (95.13%), Precision (95.34%), Recall (95.13%), and F1-Score (95.14%).

5. CONCLUSION

Fast food is often criticized for its unhealthy ingredients, such as high levels of salt, sugar, and unhealthy fats, and its contribution to the growing obesity epidemic. Despite this, fast food remains popular due to its affordability,

convenience, and widespread availability. The aim of the current study was to propose a CNN deep learning model to classify Fast Food V2 dataset. The CNN deep learning pre-trained Xception was fine-tuned for the classification task. The proposed model was trained, validated and tested using the Fast Food V2. The results showed that the proposed Xception model achieved an accuracy (95.13%), Precision (95.34%), Recall (95.13%), and F1-Score (95.14%). This proved that CNN models with modification and pre-processing of the images can classify Fast Food V2 images accurately.

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